

SURVEILLANCE CARD Disease Y - Detection of new infectious agent in wastewater/effluents

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Detection of new infectious agent (Disease Y) in wastewater and effluents from planes/ships arriving from outside of EC
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of new infectious agent causing disease in animals (with potential of causing of Disease X in humans)
3	Target species and group	Not applicable
4	Target sector / production type	Effluents from e.g. airports and ship cargo that transport animals
5	Geographical area covered	Ports of entry
6	Age group	All
7	Sampling point and strategy	Wastewater and effluents from e.g. planes/ships arriving from outside of the EC
8	Sampling time period	Year-round / not limited
9	Sampling matrix	Water/effluent samples
10	Type of disease indicators	Not applicable
11	Sampling unit	Not applicable
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Not applicable
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Following exclusion of known pathogens, additional diagnostic investigations using metagenomics, whole genome sequencing, etc.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable

15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	Not applicable
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Various, including Q-fever, Hepatitis E, COVID-19, Monkeypox
18	Additional comments	Note: It is important to assure a timely exchange and investigations of similar cases in other animal species and humans